

STANDING OUT OF THE CROWD

HOW CAN RESEARCHERS BE MORE VISIBLE

This science comic is based on these recommendations:

***Ferus, A., Gumpenberger, C., Hölbling, L., Holzner, B.,
Reitbrecht, C., Sams, B., & Schilhan, L. (2024).
Recommendations for researchers on how to increase
their visibility. Zenodo.***

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To thrive in academia,
researchers need to publish.

Many experience permanent
publication pressure ("publish
or perish") and competition.

Millions of research papers are published
every year. Therefore, standing out of the
crowd has become most important.

Traditionally, science has relied on a process called Peer Review for centuries.

This is a qualitative process of selection of scientific work by scientists (so-called peers) from the same subject areas.

Not only manuscripts of journal articles or books are reviewed but also research proposals and applications for academic positions and prizes.

Peer review was intended to ensure quality control, and scientific papers that have undergone peer review are generally more reliable sources than texts without peer review.

However, as the number of publications increases, the number and availability of peers decreases. Peer review has reached its limits, and the quality and speed of peer reviews have been deteriorating.

Preprint servers and open peer review are approaches to tackle these issues.

Since no peer can read everything, the qualitative peer review has been complemented by quantitative methods, so-called bibliometrics.

Citations are traditionally used as proxies for quality within the research community. Citation-based metrics aim to capture productivity, impact, publication strategy, prestige of publication channel or collaboration.

These metrics are used in various research assessment exercises. Therefore, researchers aim to publish in highly-ranked journals or with prestigious publishing houses that are indexed in renowned bibliometric data sources.

The best-known journal metric is the infamous Journal Impact Factor, which takes into account the publication and citation behavior of individual subject areas or certain aspects such as the 'prestige' of a journal.

However, there are potential distortions in these numbers (e.g., scientists referencing themselves to artificially increase their ranking), and as useful as citation-based metrics are, they can unfortunately also be used irresponsibly.

The "Impact Factor Chase" is such an undesirable development.

But, it is no longer just citation-based metrics that provide information about the reception of academic publications. The spectrums of what can be quantified and of interested stakeholders have become much broader. This is why various initiatives are campaigning for the responsible use of quantitative methods in research assessment.

Altmetrics are a way to map the reach and resonance of academic work in real time and in a variety of digital contexts.

For example, they include mentions in academic blogs and news articles, likes and shares on social media, citations on Wikipedia, in policy documents, and in patents.

The absolute number of traditional citations does not necessarily reflect quality. For example, research that attracts less attention in the scientific community can still be widely referenced in public debate.

Altmetrics, therefore, provide not only quantitative values but also a wealth of qualitative information that academics can use to good effect when writing CVs, applications, project proposals or research reports.

The narrative form helps to illustrate broad interest in research output or social relevance, for example, positive mentions in major news portals or in the policy documents of renowned international organisations.

We recommend that researchers familiarize themselves with these different communication channels, the opportunities they offer, and the types of information they generate.

Beyond Altmetrics here are some further recommendations for increasing visibility:

Aim for Open Access publications: they are freely accessible to the public and generally much easier to find. Search engines index the full text of an Open Access publication and make it findable.

Use Repositories: these are servers operated at universities or other research institutions where research output is archived (generally for the long-term) and usually made freely accessible worldwide without a login barrier. Standards such as unique identifiers and permanent links guarantee interoperability and reusability.

Put all your research output in your institution's **Current Research Information System (CRIS)**: this is a database that documents the overall research output of an institution. They are based on software that is either open-source, commercial, or developed by the institution itself. A CRIS usually contains metadata that describes the existing content in a structured way. It often also displays its content via a portal which is accessible to all interested parties.

Aim for Unambiguous Affiliations: correctly specifying an affiliation ensures that academic publications and research achievements are attributed to the right researchers and their institutions and increases their visibility.

Use Persistent Identifiers: The Digital Object Identifier (DOI) has become the established standard for scientific publications and research data.

The ORCID ID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) has become a standard for the unambiguous attribution of publications to their authors, since attribution just by name is prone to errors for various reasons, such as name similarities and ambiguity (especially in the case of common names), name changes (e.g. through marriage), name variations, and different spellings. The equivalent persistent identifier for institutions is ROR ID.

Be aware of the power of **Academic Search Engine Optimization (ASEO)**: Search engine optimisation (SEO) is a widely used strategy used in online marketing to improve the findability of websites and documents by search engines. Academic search engine optimisation (ASEO) relates specifically to scholarly texts.

TITLE

SUBTITLE

SEO (Search Engine Optimization)

It is good practice to keep titles short and easy to identify. Include the most important keywords or phrases in the main title, not in the subtitle. Avoid special characters that can lead to errors in the display. Abbreviations impair the search function and should only be used if they are known.

Make careful use of **Academic social networks** (such as Academia.edu and ResearchGate): these are social networks where scientists can network, interact with other professionals, and exchange publications.

But these networks are commercial and require entering personal data, which they analyse for advertising purposes. Rather use them as landing pages for your CRIS profile or ORCID record.

Following these recommendations will increase the likelihood that research output is found, read, cited or used in ways that are beneficial to society as a whole.

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